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Research Article

**A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY TO DETERMINE THE
INJUDICIOUS USAGE OF ANTIBIOTICS IN ENDODONTICS**¹Dr Muhammad Ammar Iftikhar, ²Dr Hasnain Abbas, ³Dr Hassan¹Punjab Dental Hospital, Lahore., ²Nishtar medical university and hospital, Multan.,³de'Montmorency College of Dentistry Lahore**Article Received:** July 2020**Accepted:** August 2020**Published:** September 2020**Abstract:**

Most endodontic infections can be successfully treated with surgery such as pulp extraction and root canal treatment or incision and drainage, without the need for topical or systemic antibiotics. The use of antibiotics in dental practice is characterized by an empirical prescription based on clinical and bacteriological factors that result in the development of antimicrobial resistance.

This study investigated the practice of prescribing antibiotics for various endodontic pathologies, and the results showed that 15.4% of endodontists and 65.6% of non-endodontists were prescribing antibiotics for irreversible pulpitis. In symptomatic cases of apical periodontitis, 38.5% of endodontists and 56.3% of non-endodontists prescribed antibiotics. The study involved trainees, assistants and faculty members from the dental department of Punjab Dental Hospital, Lahore for six months duration from October 2019 to March 2020.

Conclusion: *The trend of massive antibiotic use should be discouraged and dentists should be encouraged to control antibiotic prescription for optimal effect, avoid formation of resistant strains and reduce patient exposure to potential toxicity and hypersensitivity reactions.*

Key words: *careless use, antibiotics, antibiotic resistance.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Antibiotics are wonderful drugs for treating mouth infections, but their value is weakened by the emergence of bacteria that become resistant through reckless and frequent use. This immunity not only threatens the prevention and treatment of infections caused by these microorganisms; It also increases the likelihood of patients experiencing allergic reactions and unwanted side effects. About 30% of antibiotics given in primary care are considered inappropriate¹⁻². Dentists account for 10% of all antibiotics prescribed in the community, ranking fourth behind general practitioners, pediatricians and internists. Most endodontic infections are confined to the teeth and can be successfully treated with surgical procedures such as pulp extraction and root canal treatment or incision and drainage without the need for topical or systemic antibiotics, and current evidence does not support their use. complementary prophylactic or systemic antibiotics³⁻⁴. to manage. However, to obtain good results, dentists often prescribe antibiotics before surgery, in the perioperative or postoperative period, even if they apply topical fluidic antibacterial agents such as intrathecal irrigations, medications, and solid fill materials. On the other hand, it is estimated that the transient bacteremia that occurs after endodontic procedures is nothing more than bacteremia that occurs as a result of routine oral health activities such as tooth brushing⁵⁻⁶. In addition, overuse of antibiotics can lead to serious side effects, which can range from allergic reactions ranging from mild skin symptoms to anaphylactic shock and destruction of the saprophytic flora and fungal infections or colitis caused by *Clostridium difficile*. Despite the increased prevalence of antimicrobial resistance, there are some conditions that require antibiotic therapy, and include orofacial infections with elevated body temperature, and systemic symptoms such as general malaise, general body aches, trismus, and tooth re-implantation. patients with avulsions and immunocompromised patients receiving antibiotics. It will benefit the patient in preventing the spread of infection as a prophylaxis or as a support during dental procedures⁷⁻⁸. Bacteria develop resistance by mutating the genetic material or altering resistance markers, so they can thrive even in the presence of

antibiotics. Pallasch reported at least six different outcomes for antibiotic use, and only one of them could benefit patients. A positive effect means that the antibiotic interacts with the host's immune system to eliminate the infection⁹. Negative effects include the possibility of adverse toxic and allergic reactions, the emergence of bacterial strains resistant to the normal dose of antibiotics, Bacteria against traditional antibiotics and bacteria that express resistant genes. which were previously inactive genetic material that made her resistant¹⁰. A study of Lebanese dentists showed insufficient knowledge and practice in prescribing antibiotics, and 81.3% of dentists prescribed antibiotics for endodontics. This study aimed to find the application of antibiotic prescription between endodontic and non-endodontic communities in tertiary care hospitals.

METHODOLOGY:

The study was conducted after obtaining the consent of the Ethics Committee. The study involved trainees, assistants and faculty members from the dental department of Punjab Dental Hospital, Lahore for six months duration from October 2019 to March 2020. A questionnaire was developed to assess participants' antibiotic prescribing practices for various endodontic pathologies. The survey was distributed to the participants. 78 endodontists and 64 non-endodontists completed the forms. Quantitative data are presented as frequency and percentage. Chi-square test was used to compare the data. A p value of <0.05 was considered significant. Data was analyzed using SPSS version 19.

RESULTS:

In irreversible pulpitis, only 15.4% of endodontists and 65.6% of non- endodontists admitted that they prescribed antibiotics and used antibiotics for periapical periodontitis without fever and adenopathy, 38.5% of endodontists and 56.3% of non- endodontists prescribed antibiotics. Both endodontists and endodontists agreed to prescribe an antibiotic (100%) for febrile cellulitis / lymphadenopathy. The table below shows the different percentages of endodontists and non-endodontists prescribing antibiotics in different clinical cases.

TABLE 1: ANTIBIOTIC PRESCRIPTION BY ENDODONTISTS & NON ENDODONTISTS FOR VARIOUS ENDODONTIC CONDITIONS

Condition	Endodontists Pre- scribing antibiotics (Total = 78)		Non-endodontists HOs/ General Dentists) prescrib- ing antibiotics (Total = 64)		P value
	No n (%)	Yes n (%)	No n (%)	Yes n (%)	
Irreversible pulpitis	66 (84.6)	12 (15.4)	22 (34.4)	42 (65.6)	≤0.001
Periapical periodontitis with fever/ lymphadenopathy	2 (2.6)	76 (97.4)	4 (6.2)	60 (93.8)	0.28
Periapical periodontitis - without fever/ lymphadenopathy	48 (61.5)	30 (38.5)	28 (43.7)	36 (56.3)	0.34
Periapical periodontitis with sinus – with fever/ lymphadenopathy	2 (2.6)	76 (97.4)	2 (3.1)	62 (96.9)	0.84
Periapical periodontitis with sinus - without fever/ lymphadenopathy	44 (56.4)	34 (43.6)	22 (34.4)	42 (65.6)	0.009
Acute abscess – with fever/ lymphade- nopathy	0 (0)	78 (100)	0 (0)	64 (100)	-
Acute abscess – without fever/ lymph- adenopathy	38 (48.7)	40 (51.3)	10 (15.6)	54 (84.4)	≤0.001
Cellulitis - with fever/lymphadenopathy	0 (0)	78 (100)	0 (0)	64 (100)	-
Cellulitis – without fever/ lymphade- nopathy	20 (25.6)	58 (74.4)	12 (18.7)	52 (81.3)	0.33

DISCUSSION:

The rule of thumb for treating infections suggests that the antibiotic should only be helpful and not be used as a substitute for surgery. Systemic antibiotics should be used sparingly due to the possible development of allergic reactions, toxicity and side effects and the emergence of drug-resistant strains of bacteria¹¹. It should be emphasized here that antibiotics should be used only in acute conditions accompanied by symptoms such as pain, fever and swelling of soft tissues. If swelling is found, it can be treated by drainage from the root canal during preparation of the entrance cavity or by incision followed by drainage¹². On the other hand, infections that are chronic do not generally require the use of antibiotics. Following systemic administration of an antibiotic, the amount of drug reaching the infected area (canal system) is negligible and does not appear to affect bacterial growth. Therefore, in such cases, systemic antibiotic therapy is not indicated and the benefit is unlikely¹³. In living pulp teeth with normal blood supply, after systemic administration of ampicillin (500 mg), a mean concentration of about 5.5 mg / kg was found, which was usually insufficient to inhibit endodontic bacteria. reported. However, patients presenting with painful, vital teeth usually do not have pulp infected and the pain is only due to underlying inflammation of the pulp tissue. Therefore, systemic administration of antibiotics in such cases is not advisable and does not stimulate the patient's systems. An appropriate treatment plan

would be to eliminate the cause and then plan accordingly if you are having pulp or pulp therapy. The study describes the use of antibiotics in the treatment of various endodontic pathologies between endodontic and non-endodontic communities in the 3rd degree hospitals in Rawalpindi and Islamabad. The study hypothesized that there would be a clear difference in antibiotic prescribing between endodontists and endodontists, as endodontists are more likely to treat endodontic pathologies and are generally more experienced and knowledgeable than non-endodontists. Our results showed that 15.4% of endodontists and 65.6% of non-endodontists agreed to prescribe antibiotics for irreversible pulpitis. Antibiotics were prescribed by 38.5% of endodontists and 56.3% of non-endodontists in cases of asymptomatic periodontitis of the apex. A survey of Spanish dentists on the use of antibiotics in postgraduate education in endodontics showed that 22% of respondents prescribed antibiotics for irreversible pulpitis. Necrotic pulp prescribed 37% of antibiotics in the symptomatic apical periodontitis scenario and no edema. A quarter of dentists prescribed antibiotics for asymptomatic inflammation of the periapical tissues and necrotic pulp with sinuses. Postgraduate education in endodontics has been shown to increase awareness of the correct indications for antibiotics. A study of antibiotic administration by Brazilian endodontists found that 90.1% would prescribe antibiotics for an acute periapical abscess with oral swelling, while 88.1%

would prescribe antibiotics even without oral swelling and chronic inflammation of the periapical tissues. 5% of prescribed medications. In our study, 100% of endodontists prescribed antibiotics for a febrile abscess, and 51.3% prescribed antibiotics for a non-fever abscess. A study conducted on Lithuanian endodontists showed that 83% of them prescribe antibiotics for symptomatic periodontitis, and only 2% prescribe antibiotics for irreversible pulpitis. In our study, 97.4% of endodontists and 93.8% of non-endodontists prescribed antibiotics for febrile periodontitis of the apex, while 15.4% and 65.6% of patients with irreversible pulpitis prescribed antibiotics. In a study with dentists in the Islamic Republic of Iran, Shiraz found that 40% of dentists would prescribe antibiotics for non-antibiotic problems such as periapical inflammation without fever. Several guidelines and recommendations from the American Dental Association have been proposed to prevent the misuse of antibiotics.

CONCLUSION:

This study has found little application among endodontists in terms of indications for the use of antibiotics. The issue of the prudent use of antibiotics should be addressed and emphasized already in studies and through continuous medical education. In dentistry, appropriate guidelines for the prescription of antibiotics for various clinical conditions should be developed and implemented.

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